

APPLICATION OF EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN TO OPTIMISE SOLID-PHASE MICROEXTRACTION OF ORANGE JUICE FLAVOUR

Katrin Lachenmeier¹, Frank Musshoff¹, Burkhard Madea¹, and Dirk W. Lachenmeier^{2,*}

¹Institute of Legal Medicine, Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-University of Bonn, Stiftsplatz 12, D-53111 Bonn, Germany

²Chemisches und Veterinäruntersuchungsamt (CVUA) Karlsruhe, Weißenburger Str. 3, D-76187 Karlsruhe, Germany

KEYWORDS

Citrus sinensis L., solid-phase microextraction, gas chromatography, mass spectrometry, experimental design, optimisation, response surface methodology.

ABSTRACT

Experimental design is introduced as a novel procedure to optimise solid-phase microextraction for the determination of orange juice flavour using gas chromatography and mass spectrometry. A central composite design was chosen to study the effects of variation in levels of extraction time (3-15 min), extraction temperature (30-80°C) and pH value (3-11). The models fitted for the prediction of the extraction of terpene flavour compounds (limonene, myrcene, pinene, copaene, caryophyllene), as indicated by r^2 values of more than 0.97. Various surface plots were generated to describe the relationship between operating variables and predicted extraction yields. Optimum conditions with the highest desirability (minimal extraction time, highest yield for all components) were 9 min, 40°C and pH 11.

INTRODUCTION

Monoterpene hydrocarbons like pinene, limonene, and myrcene are found in juice aromas of all citrus varieties and are essential contributors to the unique aroma of the juices. Several studies confirmed that limonene is the most abundant component of this fraction; its content varies from 63% in blood orange to about 90% in bitter orange [1,2]. These characteristic compounds may be reduced due to the presence of microorganisms, exposure to high temperatures or gamma radiation [3-5]. In 1996, Steffen and Pawliszyn introduced solid-phase microextraction (SPME) for the analysis of flavour volatile compounds of orange juice [6]. In later studies, the SPME analysis was improved by varying different parameters like extraction time and temperature [7]. It was found that equilibrium could be achieved sooner with higher sample temperatures, but the total amount retained on the fibre also decreased. Other studies reported empiric results, e.g. that a 30 min exposure time at room temperature allowed the most material to be absorbed in the least time [8]. Recent results showed that SPME even can be used in combination with olfactometry to evaluate the sensorial quality of orange juices [9,10].

In this study, the influence of all basic operation parameters of SPME was examined for the first time using a statistically designed experiment. As these settings influence each other, show interactions and, additionally, a partly non-linear behaviour, the possibility to give one optimal setting for the extraction of the major flavour compounds was investigated.

* Web-address: <http://www.cvua-karlsruhe.de>

E-Mail: Lachenmeier@web.de

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents and materials

Chemicals including certified phosphate buffer solutions (pH 3-11) were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). An SPME device for the autosampler with a replaceable 100 μm polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) fibre was obtained from Supelco (Deisenhofen, Germany). The fibre was conditioned at 250°C for 1 h in the injection port of the GC according to the supplier's instructions.

Gas chromatography – mass spectrometry (GC/MS) method

The GC/MS procedure was modified from previously published methods for the quality control of Aloe vera and Noni beverages [11,12].

The analyses were performed on a model 6890 Series Plus gas chromatograph, in combination with an Agilent 5973 N MSD mass spectrometer (Chromtech, Idstein, Germany). Substances were separated on a fused silica capillary column (HP-5MS, 30 m x 0.25 mm I.D., film thickness 0.25 μm). The temperature program was applied as follows: start temperature 35°C, 10 °C/min increase up to 300 °C. The temperatures for the injection port, ion source, quadrupole and interface were set at 260 °C, 230 °C, 150 °C and 280 °C, respectively. Injection was carried out in splitless injection mode, and helium at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min was used as carrier gas. Electron impact (EI) mass spectra for the analytes were recorded in Full Scan mode.

Headspace-SPME method

500 μl of the orange juice sample were submitted into a 10 ml headspace vial in the presence of 500 μl of pH buffer solution. No further sample preparation was necessary. The vial was sealed using a silicone septum and a magnetic cap and was shaken for 5 min in the agitator of the autosampler (650 rpm, agitator on time: 0:05 min, agitator off time: 0:02 min). For absorption the needle of the SPME device containing the extraction fibre was exposed into the headspace of the vial. The compounds absorbed on the fibre were desorbed by exposing the fibre in the injection port for 5 min and then analysed.

Optimisation using experimental design

The following operation parameters of SPME were optimised with regard to highest recoveries, i.e. the highest peak areas of the volatile compounds: extraction time (3-15 min), extraction temperature (30-80°C) and pH value (3-11).

Table 1. Variables and ranges used in the central composite design

Variable	Name	Range
A	Extraction time	3-15 min
B	Extraction temperature	30-90°C
C	pH	3,7,11

In order to find the optimal working settings with minimum amount of experiments, the information contained in each experiment and furthermore the relation between the experiments has to be fully exploited by discovering interactions and non-linear dependence. The important step was to set up an orthogonal experimental design space. This was done with a central composite design [13,14]. The

chosen ranges of the variables are shown in Table 1. Studying three factors at five levels in a complete design would require 5^3 or 125 samples, whereas using a central composite design only requires 20 samples and still totally covers the experimental space and allows to calculate all interactions and non-linearities. The calculations were done using the Software Package Design Expert V6 (Stat-Ease Inc., Minneapolis, USA).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Solid-phase microextraction (SPME), discovered and developed by Pawliszyn and co-workers [15], has recently emerged as a versatile solvent-free alternative to conventional extraction procedures. A major disadvantage is the fact that SPME conditions must be extensively optimised for each analyte. In most cases the optimisation is done using the "one-factor-at-a-time" methodology as was done by our working group in previous method developments requiring each time over 100 experiments [16-19]. The systematic optimisation of SPME using experimental design strategies was proposed by Reubsat et al. in 1998 [20], and has gained a wider interest in the last years [21-30]. In this study, experimental design is used for the first time to optimise the SPME extraction of fruit juice.

Table 2. Regression coefficients in coded values for the optimisation of solid-phase microextraction of orange juice

Regression coefficient	Limonene	Myrcene	Pinene	Phellandrene	Copaene	Caryophyllene
Model	Linear	Quadratic	Quadratic	Linear	Quadratic	Quadratic
Intercept	64.02	42.59	39.14	70.16	69.62	67.80
A-Time	1.76*	4.80**	4.55***	1.08	14.62***	11.67***
B-Temperature	-30.08***	-40.50***	-41.43***	-22.39***	20.47***	24.13***
C-pH	1.59	0.80	0.34	8.05	0.82	1.45*
A ²	-	-1.39	-0.90	-	0.98	-3.78*
B ²	-	12.67***	14.93***	-	-16.64***	-17.57***
C ²	-	0.47	0.67	-	-0.60	1.71
AB	-1.24	-4.14*	-3.78**	3.44	0.98	0.41
AC	0.22	-1.37	-1.20	0.19	-1.15	-0.39
BC	-1.34	0.36	0.69	-6.09	1.05	0.57
r ²	0.9894	0.9944	0.9971	0.7699	0.9784	0.9973
C.V. [%]	2.87	6.63	5.14	17.83	6.93	3.00

* P ≤ 0.05, ** P ≤ 0.01, *** P ≤ 0.001.

Central composite designs were found to be most useful as a convenient approach to gain the optimal operation conditions of SPME in a reasonable time [20,27-30]. To keep the number of parameters as small as possible in order to avoid very complex models, the influence of the so-called salting-out effect was studied prior to the experimental design. By addition of salt the ionic strength of water increases and small polar organic analytes may be less soluble in water. In the case of the terpenes in orange juice, addition of salt lead to a significant (p<0.05) decrease of the extraction yield. All further experiments were, therefore, conducted without the addition of salt to the sample solution.

The experiments of the central composite design were evaluated using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to find the significance of the linear, quadratic and interaction terms in the response surface models. A very important step was to check the significant models for consistency by looking at the lack of fit and possible outliers.

The resulting models were significant for all terpenes. With the exception of phellandrene the models had excellent correlation coefficients larger than 0.97. The coefficients of variation also were excellent below 6.93%, especially with regard to the fact that no internal standard technique was used.

Interestingly, large differences in the extraction behaviour can be noted: limonene and phellandrene can be described by linear models, whereas the other compounds showed quadratic models.

Fig. 1. Response surface plots showing the best working area (yellow) for SPME extraction of different terpenes from orange juice (lines show the extraction yield in %)

By means of response surface analysis, the regression coefficients of the models are determined and the statistical ANOVA approach calculates the individual significance of each coefficient. Table 2 lists the regression coefficients. The factors are given in coded values, which make the six models directly comparable between each other and offer the opportunity to find the importance of each regression term in the model.

The largest influence on the extraction of all compounds had the extraction temperature (B). However, the influence is negative for limonene, myrcene, pinene and phellandrene; whereas copaene and caryophyllene are influenced positively by the extraction temperature. For myrcene, pinene, copaene and caryophyllene, the extraction temperature also had a significant quadratic influence (B^2).

The extraction time (A) had a relatively low but significant influence on all compounds with the exception of phellandrene. A significant interaction between extraction time and temperature (AB) can be noted for myrcene and pinene.

The pH of the sample solution (C) had only a very low effect on the extraction of caryophyllene but none on any other compound.

Fig. 2. Results of numerical optimisation with the goal of highest yield for all components at minimal extraction times (desirability = 0.58)

Fig. 3. Histogram of the desirabilities calculated during numerical optimisation.

With these models, it is possible to define an optimum for each compound. In Figure 1, an overlay response surface plot is shown. The plot clearly shows the very different behaviour of the compounds during SPME. Settings with high extraction yields for a single compound automatically lead to low extraction yields of other compounds. Therefore a compromise must be found, so that all compounds are extracted with satisfactory yields. A first indication is the region with extraction yields above 50%, which is marked yellow in the response contour for easy visualization. By use of the desirability function of

Myers and Montgomery [31], a numerical optimisation was calculated. The desirability is calculated by simultaneous optimisation of multiple responses and ranges from 0 to 1 (least to most desirable respectively). For SPME the goal was defined to be maximum extraction yields for all compounds at minimum extraction time (for reasons of time efficiency). The results of the numerical optimisation are shown in Figure 2. Using the setting 9 min, 40°C and pH 11, excellent extraction yields are gained for the main components limonene, myrcene, pinene, and phellandrene (>70%), as well as satisfactory yields for the minor components copaene and caryophyllene (>47%). The histogram of the desirabilities (Figure 3) confirms the fact that copaene and caryophyllene show a very different extraction behaviour, which was also obvious from the positive regression coefficients for extraction temperature. The differences can be explained by the chemical structures: limonene, myrcene, pinene and phellandrene are monoterpenes (m/z 136.2), whereas caryophyllene and copaene are sesquiterpenes (m/z 204.4).

Fig. 4. Contour plot for the combined desirability. The setting with maximum desirability is marked.

The contour plot of the desirability (Figure 4) shows that a relatively large region with desirabilities above 0.5 exists, i.e. extraction time in the range of 6 to 13 min and temperatures between 35 and 55°C.

The optimised setting allows a time-economic determination of orange juice flavour. However, it must be pointed out that non-equilibrium conditions were chosen, which make the use of an internal standard mandatory, if an accurate and precise quantification is required.

CONCLUSIONS

A methodology combining a central composite design with numerical optimisation of the desirability was introduced for the improvement of SPME. As example, the extraction of flavour compounds from orange juice was successfully demonstrated. The methodology may be applied in future for the optimisation of SPME in all application fields of analytical chemistry.

REFERENCES

1. S. Moufida, B. Marzouk. Biochemical characterization of blood orange, sweet orange, lemon, bergamot and bitter orange. *Phytochemistry* 62, 1283-1289 (2003). DOI: [10.1016/S0031-9422\(02\)00631-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-9422(02)00631-3)
2. D. Tønder, M. A. Petersen, L. Poll, C. E. Olsen. Discrimination between freshly made and stored reconstituted orange juice using GC Odour Profiling and aroma values. *Food Chem.* 61, 223-229 (1998). DOI: [10.1016/S0308-8146\(97\)00097-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-8146(97)00097-6)
3. S. Leizeron, E. Shimoni. Effect of ultrahigh-temperature continuous ohmic heating treatment on fresh orange juice. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 53, 3519-3524 (2005). DOI: [10.1021/jf0481204](https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0481204)
4. S. Leizeron, E. Shimoni. Stability and sensory shelf life of orange juice pasteurized by continuous ohmic heating. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 53, 4012-4018 (2005). DOI: [10.1021/jf047857g](https://doi.org/10.1021/jf047857g)
5. X. Fan, R. A. Gates. Degradation of monoterpenes in orange juice by gamma radiation. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 49, 2422-2426 (2001). DOI: [10.1021/jf0013813](https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0013813)
6. A. Steffen, J. Pawliszyn. Analysis of Flavor Volatiles Using Headspace Solid-Phase Microextraction. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 44, 2187-2193 (1996). DOI: [10.1021/jf950727k](https://doi.org/10.1021/jf950727k)
7. M. Jia, Q. H. Zhang, D. B. Min. Optimization of Solid-Phase Microextraction Analysis for Headspace Flavor Compounds of Orange Juice. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 46, 2744-2747 (1998). DOI: [10.1021/jf971020w](https://doi.org/10.1021/jf971020w)
8. R. Rouseff, R. Bazemore, K. Goodner, M. Naim. Gc-olfactometry with solid phase microextraction of aroma volatiles from heated and unheated orange juice. *Adv. Exp. Med. Biol.* 488, 101-112 (2001). PMID: [11548149](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11548149/)
9. B. Rega, N. Fournier, E. Guichard. Solid phase microextraction (SPME) of orange juice flavor: odor representativeness by direct gas chromatography olfactometry (D-GC-O). *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 51, 7092-7099 (2003). DOI: [10.1021/jf034384z](https://doi.org/10.1021/jf034384z)
10. B. Rega, N. Fournier, S. Nicklaus, E. Guichard. Role of pulp in flavor release and sensory perception in orange juice. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 52, 4204-4212 (2004). DOI: [10.1021/jf035361n](https://doi.org/10.1021/jf035361n)
11. K. Lachenmeier, U. Kuepper, F. Musshoff, B. Madea, H. Reusch, D. W. Lachenmeier. Quality control of Aloe vera beverages. *EJEAFChe* 4, 1033-1042 (2005). [http://ejeafche.uvigo.es/4\(4\)2005/010442005.htm](http://ejeafche.uvigo.es/4(4)2005/010442005.htm)
12. K. Lachenmeier, F. Mußhoff, B. Madea, H. Reusch, D. W. Lachenmeier. Quality control of Noni (*Morinda citrifolia*) juice. In *EURO FOOD CHEM XIII Proceedings Volume 2* (T. Eklund, M. Schwarz, H. Steinhart, H. P. Thier, P. Winterhalter, eds.), pp. 442-445. Gesellschaft Deutscher Chemiker, Frankfurt, Germany (2005).
13. D. C. Montgomery. *Design and Analysis of Experiments*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, New Jersey, USA (2005).
14. G. E. P. Box, J. S. Hunter, W. G. Hunter. *Statistics for Experimenters*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, New Jersey, USA (2005).
15. C. L. Arthur, J. Pawliszyn. Solid phase microextraction with thermal desorption using fused silica optical fibers. *Anal. Chem.* 62, 2145-2148 (1990).

16. D. W. Lachenmeier, L. Kroener, F. Musshoff, B. Madea. Determination of cannabinoids in hemp food products by use of headspace solid-phase microextraction and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 378, 183-189 (2004). DOI: [10.1007/s00216-003-2268-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-003-2268-4)
17. F. Musshoff, H. P. Junker, D. W. Lachenmeier, L. Kroener, B. Madea. Fully automated determination of cannabinoids in hair samples using headspace solid-phase microextraction and gas chromatography – mass spectrometry. *J. Anal. Toxicol.* 26, 554-560 (2002). PMID: [12501912](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12501912/)
18. K. Lachenmeier, F. Musshoff, B. Madea, E. M. Sohnus, W. Frank, D. W. Lachenmeier. Bestimmung von Anethol in Spirituosen - Vergleich von Flüssig-Flüssig-Extraktion mit Festphasenmikroextraktion (HS-SPME). *Deut. Lebensm.-Rundsch.* 101, 187-192 (2005).
19. F. Musshoff, H. P. Junker, D. W. Lachenmeier, L. Kroener, B. Madea. Fully automated determination of amphetamines and synthetic designer drugs in hair samples using headspace solid-phase microextraction and gas chromatography – mass spectrometry. *J. Chromatogr. Sci.* 40, 359-364 (2002). PMID: [12137210](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12137210/)
20. K. J. Reubsæet, N. H. Ragnar, P. Hemmersbach, K. E. Rasmussen. Determination of benzodiazepines in human urine and plasma with solvent modified solid phase micro extraction and gas chromatography; rationalisation of method development using experimental design strategies. *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 18, 667-680 (1998). DOI: [10.1016/S0731-7085\(98\)00275-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0731-7085(98)00275-1)
21. M. Polo, M. Llompарт, C. Garcia-Jares, R. Cela. Multivariate optimization of a solid-phase microextraction method for the analysis of phthalate esters in environmental waters. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1072, 63-72 (2005). DOI: [10.1016/j.chroma.2004.12.040](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2004.12.040)
22. C. Prado, J. Garrido, J. F. Periago. Urinary benzene determination by SPME/GC-MS. A study of variables by fractional factorial design and response surface methodology. *J. Chromatogr. B* 804, 255-261 (2004). DOI: [10.1016/j.jchromb.2004.01.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2004.01.020)
23. M. Llompарт, M. Lourido, P. Landin, C. Garcia-Jares, R. Cela. Optimization of a derivatization-solid-phase microextraction method for the analysis of thirty phenolic pollutants in water samples. *J. Chromatogr. A* 963, 137-148 (2002). DOI: [10.1016/S0021-9673\(02\)00646-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(02)00646-5)
24. C. Aguilar, A. Penalver, E. Pocurull, J. Ferre, F. Borrull, R. M. Marce. Optimization of solid-phase microextraction conditions using a response surface methodology to determine organochlorine pesticides in water by gas chromatography and electron-capture detection. *J. Chromatogr. A* 844, 425-432 (1999). DOI: [10.1016/S0021-9673\(99\)00393-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(99)00393-3)
25. C. Gonzalez-Barreiro, M. Lores, M. C. Casais, R. Cela. Optimisation of alachlor solid-phase microextraction from water samples using experimental design. *J. Chromatogr. A* 896, 373-379 (2000). DOI: [10.1016/S0021-9673\(00\)00679-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(00)00679-8)
26. A. Martinez-Urunuela, J. M. Gonzalez-Saiz, C. Pizarro. Optimisation of the derivatisation reaction and subsequent headspace solid-phase microextraction method for the direct determination of chlorophenols in red wine. *J. Chromatogr. A* 1048, 141-151 (2004). DOI: [10.1016/j.chroma.2004.07.026](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2004.07.026)
27. M. R. Castro, M. R. Natera, M. M. Valme Garcia, B. C. Garcia. Optimisation of headspace solid-phase microextraction for analysis of aromatic compounds in vinegar. *J. Chromatogr. A* 953, 7-15 (2002). DOI: [10.1016/S0021-9673\(02\)00122-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(02)00122-X)
28. M. R. Castro, M. R. Natera, M. M. Garcia, V, B. C. Garcia. Optimisation of headspace solid-phase microextraction for the analysis of volatile phenols in wine. *J. Chromatogr. A* 995, 11-20 (2003). DOI: [10.1016/S0021-9673\(03\)00541-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(03)00541-7)

29. J. Dron, R. Garcia, E. Millan. Optimization of headspace solid-phase microextraction by means of an experimental design for the determination of methyl tert.-butyl ether in water by gas chromatography-flame ionization detection. *J. Chromatogr. A* 963, 259-264 (2002). DOI: [10.1016/S0021-9673\(02\)00359-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(02)00359-X)
30. R. Rodil, A. M. Carro, R. A. Lorenzo, M. Abuin, R. Cela. Methylmercury determination in biological samples by derivatization, solid-phase microextraction and gas chromatography with microwave-induced plasma atomic emission spectrometry. *J. Chromatogr. A* 963, 313-323 (2002). DOI: [10.1016/S0021-9673\(02\)00644-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(02)00644-1)
31. M. H. Myers, D. C. Montgomery. *Response surface methodology*. John Wiley & Sons, New York, USA (2002).